

HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES AND PERFORMANCE OF PHARMACEUTICAL FIRMS IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract: The study evaluated the human capital development strategies and performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to; examine the relationship between employee training and output and identify the relationship between coaching and quality of products of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The target population of the study consists of three hundred and forty-one (341) senior and junior staff of the firms understudy. The whole population was used due to small number. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary sources of data were the administration of questionnaire. 253 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and Pearson correlation (r) were used to test the hypotheses. The results showed that Employee training had significant positive relationship with the output ($r = .466 < .775, p < .05$). And that coaching had significant positive relationship with the quality of products ($r = .494 < .737, p < .05$). The study concluded that employee training and coaching had significant positive relationship with output, quality of products, sales volume and revenue generation of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. The study recommended among others that Organizations should organize trainings for new employees and as well sponsor and encourage employees to attend seminars and conferences that will enhance their knowledge and increase their proficiency.

Keywords: Human capital, Development, Strategies, Performance

Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

Human capital development has emerged as a critical concern for organisations, especially in sectors like the pharmaceutical industry where the quality of human resources directly influences operational output and product quality. Due to limited funding, many firms struggle to attract and retain the right calibre and quantity of personnel capable of driving organisational goals. Furthermore, population growth continues to exert pressure on existing facilities, thereby limiting the per capita availability of essential development resources and affecting the standard of human capital formation. Over time, increasing attention has been given to crafting effective human capital development strategies, particularly in relation to employee training and coaching. These strategies are fundamental to enhancing employee experience, productivity, and satisfaction. As noted by Arun (2022), treating employees as invaluable assets means equipping them to contribute their best to organisational goals. In

pharmaceutical firms, where precision and adherence to standards are vital, human capital development strategies such as training and coaching are indispensable.

Employee training, a core strategy in human capital development, plays a vital role in improving output in pharmaceutical firms. Training enhances employees' knowledge, skills, and capabilities, enabling them to perform their duties more efficiently and with greater accuracy. Investment in employee training leads to a more competent workforce, ultimately boosting productivity and improving firm performance. As Obikwelu (2018) highlighted, the success of any development initiative is closely tied to the effective mobilisation of human capital. Coaching, another key strategy, supports continuous learning and development by providing employees with guidance and feedback tailored to their roles. This personalised development approach has a direct impact on product quality in pharmaceutical firms. Coaching helps ensure that employees not only understand technical procedures but also adhere to strict quality control standards essential in the pharmaceutical industry. Will, Thomas, and Li (2023) emphasised that human capital includes attributes such as intelligence, loyalty, and punctuality, which are often nurtured through consistent coaching.

The value of human capital lies in its intangible yet crucial contributions to organisational success. As Eigbiremolen and Anaduaka (2014) explained, human capital refers to the collective skills, education, and experiences that are fundamental to economic and organisational growth. Therefore, developing strategies to enhance these attributes is vital for pharmaceutical firms aiming to achieve high performance and remain competitive. Human capital development strategies are not only about enhancing current capabilities but also about building a workforce that can adapt to changes and sustain innovation. As Samoszuk (2017) noted, deliberate and continuous efforts to improve knowledge and skills through structured development programmes ensure that businesses derive measurable value from their human resources. In light of the above, this study seeks to examine the relationship between employee training and the output of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria, and to identify the relationship between coaching and the quality of products in these firms.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Human capital is a fundamental pillar in enhancing organisational productivity, particularly within knowledge- and skill-intensive sectors like the pharmaceutical industry. It comprises the collective skills, competencies, experiences, and attributes possessed by employees, which directly contribute to organisational efficiency, innovation, and market competitiveness. In pharmaceutical firms, where precision, quality control, and compliance are paramount, the development of human capital is essential for sustaining high levels of output and product quality. Despite the acknowledged importance of human capital, many pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State face significant challenges in harnessing its full potential. These challenges are often linked to inadequate employee training, insufficient coaching, and poor mentoring systems. The lack of structured and consistent training programmes limits the ability of employees to upgrade their skills and keep pace with technological advancements and regulatory standards in the pharmaceutical sector. Similarly, the absence of effective coaching mechanisms undermines quality assurance efforts, as employees may not receive the ongoing guidance and feedback necessary to maintain optimal performance.

Additionally, the dynamic and highly competitive business environment in which pharmaceutical firms operate demands that human capital be continuously developed to adapt to new challenges. When firms fail to prioritise human capital development strategies such as training and coaching, they risk declining productivity, reduced product quality, lower sales volumes, and diminished revenue. In many cases, employees are unable to reach their full potential due to a lack of developmental support, which negatively affects both individual and organisational performance. This problem becomes even more critical considering that the pharmaceutical industry is highly regulated and performance-driven. Inadequate investment in human capital development may result in operational inefficiencies, non-compliance with industry standards, and a weakened competitive position. Given these concerns, it becomes imperative to investigate the relationship between human capital development strategies specifically employee training and coaching and the performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the human capital development strategies and performance of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to;

- i. Examine the relationship between employee training and output of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.
- ii. Identify the relationship between coaching and quality of products of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

- i. What is the relationship between employee training and output of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the relationship between coaching and quality of products of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following alternative hypotheses guided the study;

- i. Employee training has relationship with the output of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.
- ii. Coaching has relationship with the quality of products of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Human

Humans (*Homo sapiens*) are the most common and widespread species of primate. Human beings are anatomically similar and related to the great apes but are distinguished by a more highly developed brain and a resultant capacity for articulate speech and abstract reasoning (Britannica, 2023). Humans have a large, highly developed, and complex prefrontal cortex, the region of the brain associated with higher cognition. Humans are highly intelligent, capable of episodic memory, have flexible facial expressions, self-awareness, and a theory of mind. The human mind is capable of introspection, private thought, imagination, volition, and forming views on existence. The human person exists to relate with others. The person is by nature a social being because he or she

has a tendency to go out of himself or herself to form bonds and relationships with others. Human values are a tool to manage human relations and a tool for peace when the tension is high. Humans from different parts of the world follow different religions and cultures. It means they follow different rituals, have different religious and cultural values. These differences can create a gap among humans in different parts of the world. However, the language of humanity is one force that can unite humans despite their differences. Because of technology, humans have taken on some functions of the organization and now despite technology play a new enhanced role in today's twenty-first-century economy than they did in yesteryear (Chandler, 2020).

2.1.2 Capital

The four major types of capital include working capital, debt, equity, and trading capital. The importance of being human Capital is anything that increases one's ability to generate value. It can be used to increase value across a wide range of categories, such as financial, social, physical, intellectual. Human capital is used by businesses to create products and perform services that can be used to generate revenue for the company. The most common types of human capital are intellectual and skills/talents. Intellectual refers to the intelligence of people, which can be used to successfully run a company, think creatively, solve problems, form strategies, and outperform competitors. Skills and talents are used in much the same way as intelligence to help a business operate and generate revenues (CFI, 2023). From the economists' perspective, capital is key to the functioning of any unit, whether that unit is a family, a small business, a large corporation, or an entire economy. In the broadest sense, capital can be a measurement of wealth and a resource for increasing wealth. Individuals hold capital and capital assets as part of their net worth. Companies have capital structures that define the mix of debt capital, equity capital, and working capital for daily expenditures that they use. Capital is used by companies to pay for the ongoing production of goods and services to create profit (Marshall, Caitlin & Perez, 2022).

Capital is a broad term for anything that gives its owner value or advantage, like a factory and its equipment, intellectual property like patents, or a company's or person's financial assets. Even though money itself can be called capital, the word is usually used to describe money used to make things or invest. Capital mainly denotes financial assets like deposit accounts and funds received from dedicated financing sources. Capital also represents the capital assets of any company that provides financing for day-to-day working, growth, and development (Housing, 2022). Most businesses use capital as a way to grow. Capital helps a company grow by providing the assets it needs to generate more revenue.

2.1.3 Development

Development is a process that ensures good quality of life to all the people in terms of happiness, harmony and satisfaction of essential needs. Development is a process that creates growth, progress, positive change or the addition of physical, economic, environmental, social and demographic components. Development is basically an economic concept that has positive connotations; it involves the application of certain economic and technical measures to utilize available resources to instigate economic growth and improve people's quality of life. Development is visible and useful, not necessarily immediately, and includes an aspect of quality change and the creation of conditions for a continuation of that change (SID, 2021). Development refers to activities leading to the acquisition of new knowledge or skills for purposes of growing. Organizations provide employees with

development programmes in order to enhance their capabilities. Development is a program of different combination of training. Development is designed to improve the quality and performance of present managers and provide growth for present as well as future requirements and need (Majeed and Shakeel, 2017).

Development is a process that creates growth, progress, positive change or the addition of physical, economic, environmental, social and demographic components. The purpose of development is a rise in the level and quality of life of the population, and the creation or expansion of local regional income and employment opportunities, without damaging the resources of the environment. Development is visible and useful, not necessarily immediately, and includes an aspect of quality change and the creation of conditions for a continuation of that change (SID, 2021). Organizational development is a planned, systematic change in the values or operations of employees to create overall growth in a company or organization. It differs from everyday operations and workflow improvements in that it follows a specific protocol that management communicates clearly to all employees. Organizational development is not as simple as coming up with a new idea and implementing it; every step of the process has systematic methods, from identifying problems and overcoming barriers to analyzing a new system's results. Development in an organizational is a critical and science-based process that helps organizations builds their capacity to change and achieve greater effectiveness by developing, improving, and reinforcing strategies, structures, and processes (Vulpen, 2023). Organizational change and development can be a long, sometimes overwhelming process, but organization usually begins with several goals in mind.

2.1.4 Strategies

Strategy is a general plan to achieve one or more long-term or overall goals under conditions of uncertainty. It describes how goals will be achieved by the present and acquired resources. Strategy can be intended or can emerge as a pattern of activity as the organization adapts to its environment or competes. It involves activities such as strategic planning and strategic thinking (Simeone, 2020). Strategy entails how organizations focus their efforts to achieve goals, and how they succeed. It defines a specific course of action that can be taken which defines the difference between today and tomorrow. Strategy generally involves setting goals and priorities, determining actions to achieve the goals, and mobilizing resources to execute the actions. Strategy typically involves two major processes: formulation and implementation. Formulation involves analyzing the environment or situation, making a diagnosis, and developing guiding policies. It includes such activities as strategic planning and strategic thinking. Implementation refers to the action plans taken to achieve the goals established by the guiding policy (Rumelt, 2011).

A strategic objective is most effective when it is quantifiable either by statistical results or observable data. Strategic objectives are purpose statements that help create an overall vision and set goals and measurable steps for an organization to help achieve the desired outcome. Businesses create strategic objectives to further the company vision, align company goals and drive decisions that impact daily productivity from the highest levels of the organization to all other employees (Indeed, 2023).

2.1.5 Human capital development strategies

Human capital development is vital to the growth and development of an economy. Human capital strategy is a tool that helps you strategically manage your Human Resources by an effective talent acquisition for each

position. For maximum success, your human strategic planning must combine each employee's skills with their active involvement in improving their team's performance. Human capital strategy is a tool that helps organization to strategically manage their human resources by an effective talent acquisition for each position. For maximum success, human strategic planning must combine each employee's skills with their active involvement in improving their team's performance (Singh, 2020). The term human capital development can be defined as those activities geared towards improving knowledge, sharpening the skills, instilling values, and encouraging the behaviour necessary to actualise the potentials of staff of the organization. Human capital strategy springs from the overall business strategy; the first step in formulating it is to take an overall look at the vision, mission, and values of the company. Human capital management is an incorporated push to oversee and create human abilities to accomplish altogether abnormal state of performance. Human capital management hones are set of practices that are sees individuals as resources whose present esteem can be estimated and whose future can be upgraded through venture (Chigozie, Aga & Onyia, 2018).

The growing importance and awareness of human resource issues at the strategic level in organisations has raised a number of questions about the role of line managers in recent years. Human capital management, also known simply as HCM, is a key component for businesses to ensure efficiency and cost-effectiveness. Zip, (2023) asserts that many organizations will approach human capital management by treating their workforce as an investment. This calls for strategizing ways to successfully hire top talent, engage with staff, and retain them. These processes are important because it enables the business to run smoothly and prevents unnecessary expenses in regards to re-hiring and terminating employees. Human resources functions are to be effective, there has to be a good teamwork, co-operation and consultation between line managers and human resource managers. A strategic HCM system is important for managing workforces. Not only does it help companies build a committed and skilled labor force, but it also helps boost their competitive advantage (Zip, 2023).

2.1.6.1 Employee training

Employee training refers to the process of preparing staff to accomplish their job duties. Training activities is an educational activity within an organization that is designed to improve the job performance of an individual or group. These programs typically involve advancing a worker's knowledge and skill sets and instilling greater motivation to enhance job performance. Training objectives are similar to goals or desired outcomes that provide value to the employees that participate in the training program. Employee training is a program that helps employees learns specific knowledge or skills to improve performance in their current roles. Employee development is more expansive and focuses on employee growth and future performance, rather than an immediate job role (Allen, 2023). Employee performance is considered as the main and most important human resource practice in every organization as it is the key through which organization achieve their ultimate goals and they can only achieve productivity and efficiency through higher performance of employees. Training employees for the future is the new imperative. Employee training is defined as a planned set of activities for imparting knowledge to employees, such that it leads to a growth in job skills required for organizational growth (Basumallick, 2020). More productive employees are generated when the organization begun to invest on training to improve and develop the knowledge and skills of employees and it also creates useful relationship between the

employer and employees. Creating meaningful, relatable and effective training objectives is important for the overall success of the employees who participate.

Training is considered as the course of empowering employees to accomplish their tasks with in less time and with higher efficiency, hence believed to be the most important element for administering of employees performance. Despite the potential drawbacks, training and development provides both the company as a whole and the individual employees with benefits that make the cost and time a worthwhile investment (Shelly, 2019). The identification of training needs involves organizational analysis, job analysis and individual analysis. Training and development need is a shortfall in term of employee knowledge, understanding, skills and attitudes against the job requirement. In other words, training and manpower development is not only necessary but of paramount importance to any organization that wants to survive. It is relevant to add that as the employees need training to perfects in their jobs, the organization also need the services of well trained employees to enable it achieve efficiency reduce cost and increase their profit.

2.1.6.2 Coaching

Coaching refers to a method of training, counseling or instructing an individual or a group how to develop skills to enhance their productivity or overcome a performance problem. The supervisor is called a coach while the learner is called the coachee. Coaching is a form of development in which an experienced person, called a coach, supports a learner or client in achieving a specific personal or professional goal by providing training and guidance (Passmore, 2016). Occasionally, coaching may mean an informal relationship between two people, of whom one has more experience and expertise than the other and offers advice and guidance as the latter learns; but coaching differs from mentoring by focusing on specific tasks or objectives, as opposed to more general goals or overall development. Business coaching is a type of human resource development for executives, members of management, teams, and leadership. It provides positive support, feedback, and advice on an individual or group basis to improve personal effectiveness in the business setting, many a time focusing on behavioral changes through psychometrics or 360-degree feedback for example. Business coaching is also called executive coaching. Coaches help their clients advance towards specific professional goals.

Research studies suggest that executive coaching has positive effects both within workplace performance as well as personal areas outside the workplace, with some differences in the impact of internal and external coaches (Jones, Woods & Guillaume, 2016). Business coaching is not restricted to external experts or providers. Many organizations expect their senior leaders and middle managers to coach their team members to reach higher levels of performance, increased job satisfaction, personal growth, and career development. Employee coaching guides team members on how to improve their performance through regular and systematic feedback, support, and development. Employee coaching helps the individual meet or exceeds the expectations of their role and contributes positively to the workplace. Employee coaching program is cost-effective, improves productivity, and reduces staff turnover (Carruthers, 2022). Employee coaching is primarily concerned with increasing productivity and enhancing workers' performance.

2.1.7 Performance

Performance is a particular result obtained in management, economics, marketing, etc. that print features of competitiveness, efficiency and effectiveness of the organization and its procedural and structural components. In the work place, job performance is the hypothesized conception or requirements of a role. Performance is understood as achievement of the organization in relation with. its set goals. It includes outcomes achieved, or accomplished through contribution of individuals or teams to the organization's strategic goals (May, 2020). Performance could be defined simply in terms of the achievement of quantified objectives. But performance is not only a matter of what people achieves but also how they are achieving it. A high performance result comes from appropriate behavior and the effective use of required knowledge, skills and competencies (Tutorialspoint (2022)). Using employee evaluations on a consistent basis helps employees see their growth, so that they can feel good about making progress over time. It also helps them set new goals, keeping the energy in the office high. Organization needs employees that are able to get the job done, because employee performance is critical to the overall success of the organization (Kimberlee, 2019).

2.1.7.1 Output

Output is defined as the amount of energy, labor, products, or services generated in a period by a machine, factory, business, or person. It is the number of units of goods or services produced by the businesses in that industry for sale to consumers or to businesses in other industries. Output refers to the total production of goods and services of a whole country over a given period – its gross domestic product. The term may refer to all the work, energy, goods, or services produced by an individual, company, factory or machine (Market Business News, 2022). In general, production refers to the items generated. In terms of output, the production unit implies the total number of goods produced for a given time and the different costs associated with production (Essays, 2018). Outputs often apply to the number of visited customers during a given duration. The organization needs to become accustomed if there is a decline in the output of the organization due to alteration in the external or internal environment (Kotler, 2018). Output is the quantity of goods or services produced in a given time period, by a firm, industry, or country whether consumed or used for further production. Output is the result of an economic process that has used inputs to produce a product or service that is available for sale or use somewhere else (Wikipedia, 2013). Output is the measure of production against efficiency. It crops up a lot in everyday conversation (Down, 2019).

2.1.7.2 Quality of products

Customer satisfaction is determined by the quality and price of the products desired by the customer. Product quality is a critical determinant of consumer satisfaction. It refers to how well a product satisfies customer needs, serves its purpose and meets industry standards. Product quality earns customer loyalty, helps establish brand recognition and manages costs. Garvin's eight dimensions of Product Quality in Performance, Features, Reliability, Conformance, Durability, Serviceability, Aesthetics and Perceived quality are dimensions of Product Quality that affect Customer Satisfaction which impacts Loyalty (Ling & Mansori, 2018). It is important to note that the quality of the product is not reviewed by the company standpoint; it is seen from the perspective of the customer. If the perceived product quality is in line with the expectation, then the customer will perceive the

product quality as a good quality and also feel satisfied. Conversely, if the perceived product quality is not as expected, then the quality of the product as the customer perceived is qualified as a bad product quality. Thus, the qualification of both bad and good product depends on the ability of the company to meet the customer expectations. Product quality is the extent to which a good service or combination thereof solves a problem or meets a need. For a product to have any real value, it has to have some kind of quality or, hopefully, a high level of quality. In other words it needs to actually solve a problem for the consumer or meet a need (Gordon, 2022). Product Quality is the collection of all the features and characteristics of a product that contribute to its ability to meet the customer needs and requirements. It's the ability of the product to fulfill what the end user wants and perceives as value. Product quality is single most important parameter for a product, brand or organization. The quality determines the customer experience and repeat business. If the product quality is poor and the product is not able to do its job reliably and safely then the brand image suffers (MBA, 2021). Consumers and customers often demand changes. These changes further drive the service provisioning and delivery forward, with increasing demand for quality. Product Quality is the collection of all the features and characteristics of a product that contribute to its ability to meet the customer needs and requirements. It's the ability of the product to fulfill what the end user wants and perceives as value. For a product to be of good quality it should be reliable and perform all its functions smoothly. The success of any corporate service provider can be measured in terms of its customers' attitude towards the service delivery process means service quality management dimensions will be the dominant elements in the customers' evaluations of a given service provider. While product quality is measured through its ability to meet the user's requirement and the value of its features and characteristics, service quality is more of a comparison of the customer expectations and the service performance (Rahim, 2016).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Ability-Motivation-Opportunity Theory

The AMO framework was initially proposed by Bailey (1993). Drawing on the classical Ability Motivation Opportunity (AMO) framework emphasizing the necessity of employees to possess abilities, motivation and be given opportunity to perform. This theory is used to spot the terrain for further study on green human resources management as an innovation in Nigeria organization setting. As most innovations are related to product development, this study highlights GHRM practices as a process improvement in responding to the current trend shifting from pro-economic to pro-social then pro-environment. This way, under the AMO concept, this study scrutinizes the necessity to initiate GHRM practices indigenous manufacturing firm as a process development by integrating people, process, technology and the organization. Sustainability has led to soaring growth of literature on green marketing, green accounting, green retailing, green supply chain management and green general management. Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) studies on how this field contributes to preserving the environment is hardly found and the polarization between "Best fit" and best practice in HRM make difficult to measure human resource management output. AMO theory stresses that employee' abilities, motivations, and opportunities contribute to organizational performance; this is an integrating perspective illustrating why and how leaders and strategic HRM practices promote firm performance (Ismi, Haslinda and Budiono, 2016).

The AMO theory suggests that there are three independent work system components that shape employee characteristics and contribute to the success of the organization. According to the theory, organizational interests are best served by a system that attends to the employee's ability, motivation, and opportunity (AMO). Organization need to align well with the AMO theory to: Increases the ability of the employee; Motivates employees and Provides opportunities to contribute to the company. Organization utilizes the AMO theory to provide organizational leaders with a management tool that can impact performance. If any one of the three characteristics is missing, performance is likely to be inhibited, but if all three are present, then performance is likely to be enhanced. High employee performance is a strong factor that contributes to organizational success (Amber, 2019).

2.3 Empirical review

Ozoko, and Ede, (2020), conducted a study on Effect of Learning on the Product Quality of Chemical and Pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study used the survey approach. The primary sources were personal interview and the administration of questionnaire. A population of 3,418 staff was used. The population of the study was drawn from the staff of these organizations under study using a stratified sampling method. To determine the adequate sample size of 346, using Freund and William statistic formula. A 326 staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 94 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.77 which was also good. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z- test statistics tool. The findings indicated that employee absorbed knowledge has positive effect on standard product of manufacturing firms in Enugu State $Z(95, n = 346) = 5.635, p > 0.05$, Employee undergoing a process has positive effect on the features of manufacturing firms in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 346) = 5.819, p > 0.05$, employee retention of knowledge has positive effect on the reliability of products of manufacturing firms in Enugu State. $Z(95, n = 346) = 5.984, p > 0.05$.

Mbah, and Maduafor, (2022), conducted a study on Knowledge Management and Organizational Performance of Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design. This study was carried out in Enugu State, Nigeria. Therefore, the population of the study comprised 1590. The sample size consisted 310 was obtained using statistical formula devised by Borg and Gall. This study made use of primary source of data. The research instrument was questionnaire, which was subjected to face and content validity procedures. Data gathered was retested using Cronbach Alpha. The data collected were analyzed using simple percentages to answer the research questions while multiple regression was used in test the hypotheses. The result shows that knowledge accessibility has a significant positive influence on market share in pharmaceutical manufacturing firms; Knowledge sharing has a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction in pharmaceutical manufacturing firms and Knowledge creation has a significant positive influence on employee efficiency in pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Wassim (2023), conducted a study on Study the Impact of the Training Strategy on Organizational Performance Indicators: Survey on Syrian Pharmaceutical Companies. This research aims to examine the extent to which the training strategy developed by pharmaceutical manufacturing companies in Syria affects organizational

performance assessment indicators. In this study, the researcher relied on the following indicators as indicators for evaluating organizational performance: worker results, business results, client results. The comprehensive accounting method was used to determine the size of the research sample, and the analytical descriptive approach was based on the survey method, and a questionnaire was used according to the Likert fifth scale, the response rate was 91.875%, and the data was analyzed using the SPSS software. The study drew conclusions, most notably: there is a moral impact of the training strategy on the indicators of organizational performance assessment in Syrian pharmaceutical manufacturing companies.

Aktar, (2023). Conducted a study on the effect of training and development methods on employee satisfaction and performance in commercial banks. The present study selected seven popular methods of training and development used frequently by the Commercial Bank of Bangladesh. For this study, it has been hypothesized that training and development methods positively impact employees' satisfaction and performance from the perspective of commercial banks in Bangladesh. The current study is empirical in nature, implying the collection of both primary and secondary data. A structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data from employees of twelve commercial banks. The 250 questionnaires were distributed to the employees and collected. After sorting out the primary data, 200 questionnaires were used for analysis. The present study revealed that the informal learning method of training and development has a significant positive impact on employees' satisfaction and performance in commercial banks in Bangladesh. The other two methods of training and development, i.e. job rotation and seminars, have a significant positive impact on creating employee satisfaction in the commercial banks of Bangladesh.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed Descriptive research design. Both secondary and primary sources of data were utilized in the study. The area of the study was Enugu state. The population of the study consisted of five (5) pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu state, Nigeria, Nigeria with minimum capital base of 10 million and minimum of fifty (50) employees. The employees were made up of junior and senior employees. These made up the population of study of three hundred and forty-one (341) of Junior and senior staff of organizations under study. The Questionnaire was used for data collection. Data from the questionnaire were analyzed with the aid of SPSS version 23 using simple, percentages. Data from the questionnaire were further analyzed using simple percentages, mean and standard deviation. For the 5-point Likert scale questions. Pearson Product moment correlation was adopted in the test of hypotheses.

DATA ANALYSES AND RESULT PRESENTATION

4.1 Data relating to research question

4.1.1 The relationship between employee training and output of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

Table 4.1.1: Responses on the relationship between employee training and output of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		

1	Employee training reduces staff turnover in the organisation.	515 103 40.7	256 64 25.3	48 16 6.3	58 29 11.5	41 41 16.2	918 253 100%	3.63	1.503	Agree
2	Training lower maintenance cost by reducing equipment breakdowns.	400 80 31.6	256 64 25.3	75 25 9.9	36 18 7.1	66 66 26.1	833 253 100%	3.29	1.599	Agree
3	Creativity for new products ideas are promoted with training in the organisation.	445 89 35.2	312 78 30.8	78 26 10.3	40 20 7.9	40 40 15.. 8	915 253 100%	3.62	1.433	Agree
4	Training improves employee relation rates and quality of service.	515 103 40.7	280 70 27.7	21 7 2.8	84 42 16.6	31 31 12.3	931 253 100%	3.68	1.452	Agree
5	Effective training saves labour by reducing time spent in the organisation.	485 97 38.3	280 70 27.7	54 18 7.1	40 20 7.9	48 48 19.0	907 253 100%	3.58	1.522	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.56	1.5018	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.1.1, 167 respondents out of 253 representing 66.0 percent agreed that employee training reduces staff turnover in the organisation with mean score 3.63 and standard deviation of 1.503. Training lower maintenance cost by reducing equipment breakdowns 144 respondents representing 56.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.29 and standard deviation of 1.599. Creativity for new products ideas are promoted with training in the organisation 167 respondents representing 66.0 percent agreed with mean score of 3.62 and standard deviation of 1.433. Training improves employee relation rates and quality of service 173 respondents representing 68.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.68 and 1.452. Effective training saves labour by reducing time spent in the organisation 167 respondents representing 66.0 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.58 and standard deviation 1.522.

4.1.2 The relationship between coaching and quality of products of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

Table 4.1.2.: Responses on the relationship between coaching and quality of products of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

	5	4	3	2	1	∑FX	-	SD	Decision
	SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		

1	Good coach improves quality through facilitation in the organisation.	475 95 37.5	368 92 36.4	21 7 2.8	88 44 17.4	15 15 5.9	967 253 100%	3.82	1.268	Agree
2	A quality coach promotes education and experimentation in the pharmaceutical firm.	380 76 30.0	368 92 36.4	3 1 .4	76 38 15.0	46 46 18.2	873 253 100%	3.45	1.500	Agree
3	Coach helps employees learn and improve their lives through producing quality products.	420 84 33.2	376 94 37.2	18 6 2.4	80 40 15.8	29 29 11.5	923 253 100%	3.65	1.380	Agree
4	Advice based on personal experience increased standard of the products.	440 88 34.8	296 74 29.2	69 23 9.1	12 6 2.4	62 62 24.5	879 253 100%	3.47	1.572	Agree
5	The use of advice based on skills facilities growth in the organisation.	545 109 43.1	236 59 23.3	42 14 5.5	86 43 17.0	28 28 11.1	937 253 100%	3.70	1.443	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.618	1.432	6

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 4.1.2., 187 respondents out of 253 representing 73.9 percent agreed that good coach improves quality through facilitation in the organisation with mean score 3.82 and standard deviation of 1.268 A quality coach promotes education and experimentation in the pharmaceutical firm 168 respondents representing 73.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.45 and standard deviation of 1.500. Coach helps employees learn and improve their lives through producing quality products 178 respondents representing 70.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.65 and standard deviation of 1.380. Advice based on personal experience increased standard of the products 162 respondents representing 64.0 percent agreed with mean score of 3.47 and 1.572. The use of advice based on skills facilities growth in the organisation 168 respondents representing 66.4 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.70 and standard deviation 1.443.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypotheses one: Employee training has relationship with the output of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

Table 4.2.1 shows Pearson Correlation on employee training has relationship with the output of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

Correlations

		Employee training reduces staff turnover in the organisation.	Training lower maintenance cost by reducing equipment breakdowns.	Creativity for new products ideas are promoted with training in the organisation.	Training improves employee relation rates and quality of service.	Effective training saves labour by reducing time spent in the organisation.
Employee training reduces staff turnover in the organisation.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 .683** .000 253	.683** .000 253	.670** .000 253	.586** .000 253	.602** .000 253
Training lower maintenance cost by reducing equipment breakdowns.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.683** .000 253	1 .589** .000 253	.589** .000 253	.471** .000 253	.466** .000 253
Creativity for new products ideas are promoted with training in the organisation.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.670** .000 253	.589** .000 253	1 .587** .000 253	.587** .000 253	.775** .000 253
Training improves employee relation rates and quality of service.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.586** .000 253	.471** .000 253	.587** .000 253	1 .656** .000 253	.656** .000 253
Effective training saves labour by	Pearson Correlation	.602**	.466**	.775**	.656**	1

reducing time spent in the organisation.	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	253	253	253	253	253

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.2.1. Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on employee training and output showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.466 < .775$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that employee training had positive significant relationship with the output of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria ($r=.466 < .775$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r =.466 < .775, p >.05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r=.466 < .775$) is greater than the table value of $.000$, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that employee training had positive significant relationship with the output of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .466 < .775, p>.05$).

4.2.2 Hypotheses two: coaching has relationship with the quality of products of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

Table 4.2.2 shows Pearson Correlation on coaching has relationship with the quality of products of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

Correlations

	Good coach improves quality through facilitation in the organisation.	A quality coach promotes education and experimentation in the pharmaceutical firm.	Coach helps employees learn and improve their lives through producing quality products.	Advice based on personal experience increased standard of the products.	The use of advice based on skills facilities growth in the organisation.
Good coach improves quality through facilitation in the organisation.	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	1 .723** .000	.722** .000	.584** .000	.589** .000

A quality coach promotes education and experimentation in the pharmaceutical firm.	N	253	253	253	253	253
	Pearson Correlation	.723**	1	.737**	.589**	.594**
Coach helps employees learn and improve their lives through producing quality products.	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	253	253	253	253	253
Advice based on personal experience increased standard of the products.	Pearson Correlation	.722**	.737**	1	.589**	.571**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
The use of advice based on skills facilities growth in the organisation.	N	253	253	253	253	253
	Pearson Correlation	.584**	.589**	.589**	1	.494**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	253	253	253	253	253
	Pearson Correlation	.589**	.594**	.571**	.494**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	253	253	253	253	253

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.2.2. Showed the Pearson correlation matrix on coaching and quality of products showing the correlation coefficients, significant values and the number of cases. The correlation coefficient shows $.494 < .737$. This value indicates that correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2 tailed) and implies that coaching had positive significant relationship with the quality of products of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria ($r = .494 < .737$). The computed correlations coefficient is greater than the table value of $r = .000$ with at alpha level for a two-tailed test ($r = .494 < .737, p > .05$).

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to accept the null hypothesis if the computed r is less than the tabulated r otherwise reject the null hypothesis.

Decision

Since the computed ($r = .494 < .737$) is greater than the table value of .000, we reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, we concluded that coaching had positive significant relationship with the quality of products of pharmaceutical firms in Enugu State, Nigeria as reported in the probability value of ($r = .494 < .737, p > .05$).

5.1 Summary of Findings

The following findings were made by the study

- i. Employee training had positive significant relationship with the output of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria ($r = .466 < .775, p < .05$).
- ii. Coaching had positive significant relationship with the quality of products of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria ($r = .494 < .737, p < .05$).

5.2 Conclusion

The study concluded that employee training and coaching had significant positive relationship with output and quality of products of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State. Human component is the most important component required in every organization. Developed human capital creates value and generates revenue, able to spot opportunities and take advantage of them, able to develop and implement strategies that make the organization a market leader, and ultimately optimizes organizational performance. Human capital development is very crucial in order to have the maximum utilization of the manpower for the benefit and advantage of both the employees and the organization.

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendation were made by the study

- i. Organizations should organize trainings for new employees and as well sponsor and encourage employees to attend seminars and conferences that will enhance their knowledge and increase their proficiency.
- ii. Teamwork should be encouraged by managers and supervisors as it will help in sharing ideas that will be of great benefit to the organization and as well help to create a conducive working environment in the organization.

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